

DEVELOPMENT OF A PLANT-BASED FUNCTIONAL DRINK USING APPLE JUICE AND MORINGA OLEIFERA LEAF EXTRACT

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Abstract: Developing foods with boosted functionality to minimize the potential side effects of oxidative/nitrosative stress and support the immune system while responding to consumers' needs and preferences is a challenging trend in the food industry. The use of Moringa oleifera leaves, characterized by their high nutritional value and multiple pharmacological properties, is emerging in food applications. The present study aimed at developing a functional ready-to-serve apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves (A.F.D.MO), studying the antioxidant, physicochemical, and nutritional properties, estimating the sensory shelf-life for 14 days, and evaluating the consumer acceptance. Apple juice, aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera, orange juice, and lemon juice were added in the following proportions (58:20:20:2) and pasteurized at 90 °C for 30 seconds. The newly developed fruit blend appeared to have a pH of 3.5 and total soluble solids of 10%, with a high antioxidant activity at 1 mg/ml concentration and recorded to be 90.4%. A.F.D.MO was found to be microbiologically safe and retained its sensory attributes during 14-day storage at refrigeration and even at ambient temperature. The sensory evaluation of the apple-based juice fortified with 20 % aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves portrayed a highly accepted fruit juice blend by potential Lebanese consumers owing to its taste. Freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaf extract was found to be a suitable natural preservative and a functional component with health-promoting properties that could support the body's immune system.

Keywords: Freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves, Apple-based juice, Immune system, Functional foods, Antioxidant activity

INTRODUCTION

Consumers' concerns about health and disease prevention with interest in improving the quality of their diet motivated the scientific community to focus on developing functional foods as sources of nutrients and bioactive components with antioxidant properties (Baker et al., 2022). Antioxidants can mitigate oxidative/nitrosative stress and its consequences. Oxidative/nitrosative stress is reported to deteriorate cells and tissues and contribute to the pathogenesis of many metabolic and inflammatory diseases. Antioxidants can be endogenous, produced in the body as enzymes or nonenzymatic compounds. They can also be exogenously supplied from food or as dietary supplements and preservatives. It is well-documented that

exogenous antioxidants can support the body's endogenous antioxidative defense (Pisoschi et al., 2021). Moreover, a growing body of evidence confirms that nutrients with antioxidant properties are

vital for an optimal immune system (Gombart et al., 2020; Khadim & Al-Fartusie, 2021). Recent concerns about the side effects of synthetic antioxidants conjointly with the rising prevalence of infectious and non-communicable diseases have shifted the attention towards medicinal plants possessing functional bioactive components with antioxidant and immunomodulation properties (Ayoka et al., 2022; Khadim & Al-Fartusie, 2021). *Moringa oleifera* (MO) is among the medicinal plants that gained attention. Their leaves became a research interest worldwide due to their high nutritional value, bioactive substances, multiple pharmacological properties, and immunomodulatory characteristics (Kashyap et al., 2022; Mehwish et al., 2022). MO leaves appeared to be a valuable source of macro and micronutrients. They are high in digestible protein encompassing ten essential amino acids (Kashyap et al., 2022; Rathnayake et al., 2019). MO leaves comprise sulfur-containing amino acids, namely methionine and cystine, which are reported as powerful antioxidants (Rathnayake et al., 2019). The leaves contain fatty acids with appreciable quantities of omega-3. They appeared to be rich sources of minerals and vitamins with antioxidant activity (El-zainy et al., 2017; Kashyap et al., 2022; Rathnayake et al., 2019). Recent studies on MO leaves have elucidated that they contain phenolic compounds, carotenoids, alkaloids, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, and other bioactive substances. These nutritional and functional properties encourage the exploration of MO leaves in food applications (Hassan et al., 2021; Kashyap et al., 2022; Rathnayake et al., 2019). It was found that freeze-drying is the best method of preserving the phytoconstituents and biological properties of MO leaves (Ademiluyi et al., 2018). To the best of the authors' knowledge, the use of freeze-dried MO leaves in food applications was not extensively studied. Therefore, studying their use as value-added ingredients in food products that satisfy consumers' expectations is imperative.

Fruit juices are among the active functional food categories due to their sensory properties and nutritional value. Apple juice is one of the most popular products in the world in terms of production and international exchange. Apple juice is considered an ideal fortification candidate, distinguished in flavor and intermediate in bioactive compounds (Grobelna et al., 2019; Nour, 2022). Fresh orange and lemon juices are good sources of bioavailable antioxidant compounds (Miles & Calder, 2021; Zou et al., 2016). Citrus juices contain odoractive volatile compounds. Therefore they were selected as ingredients that contribute to the flavor profile of the functional juice (Wang et al., 2020).

The present study aimed (1) to develop a functional ready-to-serve apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves (A.F.D.MO), (2) study its antioxidant activity, physicochemical, and nutritional properties, (3) assess its sensory shelf-life for 14 days, (4) and evaluate the consumer acceptance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials Procurement

the varieties of fruits were purchased from the local Lebanese market. The apples (*Malus domestica*) "Red Delicious", oranges (*Citrus sinensis*) "Valencia", and lemons (*Citrus limon*) were of premium quality, matured, and freshly harvested. MO leaves were obtained as organic, freeze-dried, and vacuum packed imported from India via "Dr. Moringa Company, Beirut, Lebanon."

Juices Preparation

Apple juice

Apples were sorted, washed thoroughly, cut into quarters, and submerged in distilled water containing 30 ml of orange and 30 ml of lemon juices. The apple cuts were then blanched at 75OC, drained, and ground into small pieces using an electrical food processor (Magimix MX5200B Cuisine System XL Food Processor). The apple sauce obtained was placed in a muslin cloth and cold pressed using a hydraulic press juicer extractor machine to get apple juice without pulp.

Citrus juices

the citrus fruits were sorted, washed thoroughly, cut into halves, and squeezed using an electrical juicer (Bifinett KH 85 Citropress, Germany). The juices obtained were filtered using a sterilized cheesecloth.

MO extract

the freeze-dried MO leaves were homogenized to a fine powder using an electric grinder (Moulinex electric coffee grinder). The aqueous extract was obtained following the method applied by El-Zainy et al. (El-zainy et al., 2017). 4g of MO powder was infused with 50 ml of boiling water at 100OC for 5 minutes, then filtered via sterilized muslin cloth to obtain a filtrate.

All juices and MO aqueous extracts were freshly prepared and mixed immediately at different proportions.

Apple-based juice with aqueous extract of freeze-dried MO leaves juice

The A.F.D.MO was obtained by mixing apple juice, MO extract, orange juice, and lemon juice in the following proportion (58:20:20:2). The mixture obtained was placed in sanitized closed glass bottles and pasteurized in a water bath at 90OC for 30 seconds. Samples of the A.F.D.MO were stored at two different temperature conditions: refrigeration temperature of 4°C (RT) and ambient temperature fixed at 25°C (AT) away from light.

Table 1: The pH and total soluble solids of apple juice, orange juice, lemon juice, and A.F.D.MO.

Physicochemical characteristics at To	Apple Juice	Orange Juice	Lemon Juice	A.F.D.MO
pH	3.9 ± 0.02	4.3 ± 0.03	2.2 ± 0.02	3.5 ± 0.02
Total soluble solids %	11 ± 0.00	12 ± 0.01	8 ± 0.00	10 ± 0.03

The values represent means ± standard deviation.

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves.

Antioxidant Activity

The DPPH free radical scavenging activity of A.F.D.MO at different concentration levels was significantly lower than Vitamin C (p-value) (Table 2). Although a statistical difference was observed between the antioxidant activity of A.F.D.MO at a concentration of 1 mg/ml (90.4 ± 0.31%) and that of

control Vitamin C extract (100 ± 0.00%) (p-value ≤ 0.05), it was noted that A.F.D.MO is considered to have a high antioxidant property.

The DPPH scavenging capacity of A.F.D.MO was shown to be superior to the scavenging capacity previously reported for pasteurized apple (24.95%), orange (58.90%), and lemon (81.53%) juices (Benattouche et al., 2021; Li et al., 2018; Uçan et al., 2016). A.F.D.MO presented a higher DPPH scavenging capacity than the orange juice mixture prepared by Hashemi et al., which was recorded as 72.68% (Hashemi et al., 2018).

Although 20% MO leaf extract was used in both studies, the MO leaves in the current study were freeze-dried, whereas in the Hashemi et al. study, they were hot-dried.

The high antioxidant activity of A.F.D.MO could be due to the joint action of bioactive compounds such as vitamin C, phenols, and flavonoids (chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, and rutin) already detected in the freeze-dried MO leaves (Ademiluyi et al., 2018; Zou et al., 2016).

The synergistic effect of bioactive compounds co-delivered by the freeze-dried MO leaves and the citrus juices could explain the further enhancement of A.F.D.MO antioxidant activity (Vichaibun & Kanchanaphu, 2019).

The findings of the current study support the use of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves to enhance the functionality of food products.

Table 2: DPPH free radical scavenging activity of A.F.D.MO as compared to Vitamin C

Volume of extract in test tube	DPPH Inhibition % A.F.D.MO	DPPH Inhibition % Vitamin C
250 µl	58.6 ± 0.10 a	97 ± 0.35 b
500 µl	72 ± 0.14 a	96.7 ± 0.11 b
750 µl	80.4 ± 0.20 a	98 ± 0.47 b
1000 µl	90.4 ± 0.31 a	100 ± 0.00 b

µl: microliter; %: percentage.

The values represent means ± standard deviation. Means in the same row not sharing the same alphabetical letter are significantly different (p-value).

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves.

Microbiological Analysis

The microbiological results are presented in Table 3. According to L.I.B.N.O.R. standards, bacteria, yeasts, and molds were within the acceptable limit. Salmonella species tested on the production day (To) were not detected. A.F.D.MO was found to be microbiologically safe.

Table 3: Microbiological analysis of the A.F.D.MO at production day (To)

Microorganisms tested at To	Result	Acceptable limit according to L.I.B.N.O.R.
Aerobic colonycount at 30°C	1CFU /ml	5.103 -104

Total coliforms at 37°C	<1 CFU/ml	10-100
Yeast and Molds count at 25°C	<10 CFU /ml	10 ² -10 ³
E. coli at 44°C	< 1CFU/ml	<10
Salmonella at 41.5°C	Not detected	Absence

CFU: colony forming unit; ml: milliliter.

L.I.B.N.O.R.: Lebanese Standards Institution.

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves.

Sensory Shelf-Life Estimation

The changes in the sensory attribute scores (taste, odor, color, texture, and overall acceptability) evaluated at 4°C for 14 days are presented in Table 4. Taste and odor received the highest score (5) relative to other parameters from T₀ to T₁₄. As for color, a significant change occurred at T₃ after production. Nevertheless, the alteration in texture and overall acceptability was not significant during the 14 days.

Results of the changes in the sensory attributes at ambient temperature (25°C) for 14 days are shown in Table 5. The odor retained a high score (5) for 14 days after production, whereas changes in taste between T₆ and T₉, in color between T₀ and T₆, and in overall acceptability between T₃ and T₉ were significant.

The overall acceptability scores of the A.F.D.MO at T₁₄ were recorded to be 4.66 at 4°C and 4 at 25°C, reflecting that the newly developed fruit blend maintained its sensory attributes for 14 days.

The aqueous extract of freeze-dried MO leaves could have contributed to retaining the sensory quality of A.F.D.MO throughout the storage period at refrigeration as well as ambient temperature. MO leaf extract has been reported to possess antibacterial and antifungal activities due to its phytochemicals with antimicrobial properties, including tannins, phenolic compounds, and flavonoids (Ahmed et al., 2023).

The role of MO leaf extract as a natural preservative in juices has been confirmed previously (El-zainy et al., 2017; Hashemi et al., 2018). In addition, A.F.D.MO was prepared under good manufacturing practices, preserved in sanitized bottles, and pasteurized at 90°C for 30 seconds. Pasteurization is used to inactivate heat-sensitive spoilage and food poisoning microorganisms such as vegetative bacteria, molds, and yeasts, and to reduce the activity of some enzymes such as pectin esterase and pectin methyl esterase (Ağçam et al., 2018).

The current study's findings also support the use of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves as a natural preservative in the food industry.

Table 4: Organoleptic properties of A.F.D.MO during storage at a refrigeration temperature of 4°C (RT) from the day of production (To) up to 14 days after production (T14)

Organoleptic properties	Storage Period (days)				
	To	T3	T6	T9	T14
Taste	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a
Odor	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a
Color	5.00 ± 0.00 b	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a
Texture	4.00 ± 0.00 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a
Overall Acceptability	4.66 ± 0.57 a	4.66 ± 0.57 a	4.66 ± 0.57 a	4.33 ± 0.57 a	4.66 ± 0.57 a

The values represent means ± standard deviation for each organoleptic property at different times. Means in the same row not sharing the same alphabetical letter are significantly different (p-value).

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves.

Table 5: Organoleptic properties of A.F.D.MO during storage at ambient temperature of 25°C (AT) from the day of production (To) up to 14 days after production (T14)

Organoleptic properties	Storage Period (days)				
	To	T3	T6	T9	T14
Taste	5.00 ± 0.00 b	5.00 ± 0.00 b	5.00 ± 0.00 b	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a
Odor	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a	5.00 ± 0.00 a

Color	5.00 ± 0.00 b	4.33 ± 0.57 ab	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a
Texture	4.00 ± 0.00 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a	3.66 ± 0.57 a
Overall Acceptability	5.00 ± 0.00 b	5.00 ± 0.00 b	4.33 ± 0.57 ab	4.33 ± 0.57 a	4.00 ± 0.00 a

The values represent means ± standard deviation for each organoleptic property at different times. Means in the same row not sharing the same alphabetical letter are significantly different (p-value).

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried Moringa oleifera leaves.

Consumer Acceptance

The results of the sensory evaluation reflecting the acceptance of A.F.D.MO in terms of sensory attributes (taste, odor, color, texture, and overall acceptability) are presented in Figure 1.

The mean values of the five attributes' scores based on the five-point hedonic scale ranged between 4.3 for odor, 4.48 for taste and overall acceptability, 4.5 for texture, and 4.59 for color.

The results also showed that 96% of the participants proclaimed the overall acceptability of the product (Figure 2).

The correlation between overall acceptability and other sensory attributes (color, odor, taste, and texture) revealed that taste had the highest correlation with overall acceptability ($r = 0.794$), whereas texture had a weaker correlation ($r = 0.387$) (Table 6).

Developing new food products with high-quality characteristics while responding to consumers' needs and preferences is a challenging trend in the food industry (Pinto, Vilela, and Cosme, 2022). Therefore, the sensory quality of the newly developed fruit blend plays a vital role in consumer satisfaction.

Findings from the sensory evaluation revealed that A.F.D.MO is a well-accepted natural functional fruit juice blend that could be introduced into the Lebanese market for health-conscious consumers. The overall acceptability of A.F.D.MO appeared to be higher than the blend prepared by Hashemi et al. (Hashemi et al., 2018).

Table 6: Correlation between the overall acceptability and the sensory attributes of A.F.D.MO

	Color	Odor	Taste	Texture
Overall Acceptability	.463**	.433**	.794**	.387**

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

Figure 1

Figure 1: Hedonic analysis of A.F.D.MO

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

Figure 2:

Figure 2: Overall acceptability of A.F.D.MO by the consumers

Nutrition Facts

The nutrient composition of A.F.D.MO presented in Table 7 reveals that 100 g of the apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves yields 45 calories and contains around 11 g carbohydrates, with negligible protein and fat content, and no trans-fat or added sugar. Even though nutrients with potential antioxidant properties such as vitamin E and β -carotene were detected in small amounts, A.F.D.MO appeared to contain a good amount of vitamin C (15 mg/100 g) owing to the aqueous extract of MO leaves and the citrus juices (El-zainy et al., 2017; Miles & Calder, 2021).

Vitamin C is documented to be one of the micronutrients with strong evidence for supporting the immune system (Gombart et al., 2020).

Table 7: Nutrient composition of A.F.D.MO

Per 100 g	A.F.D.MO
Calories (Kcal)	45
Total fat (g)	0.18
Saturated fat (g)	0
Trans Fat (g)	0
Cholesterol (g)	0
Sodium (mg)	3.32
Total carbohydrates (g)	10.86
Dietary fibers (g)	0.26
Total Sugar (g)	9
Added Sugar (g)	0
Protein (g)	0.31
Vitamin C- Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)	15
Vitamin E – Alpha Tocopherol Acetate (mg/100g)	0.55
Carotenoids as β -carotene (mcg/100g)	8.11

A.F.D.MO: Apple-based juice fortified with an aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves

CONCLUSION

The current study revealed that apple-based juice fortified with a 20% aqueous extract of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaves is a highly accepted functional fruit juice blend characterized by high antioxidant activity and sensory shelf-life stability for 14 days at both refrigeration and ambient temperatures.

Freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract was found to be a suitable natural preservative and a functional component with health-promoting properties that could play a role in supporting the body's immune system.

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